

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF THE PbSe-MnSe SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

In the PbSe-MnSe system, alloys were synthesized in a wide range of concentrations to study phase equilibrium. The nature of the chemical interaction in the PbSe-MnSe system was studied, and its T-x phase diagram was constructed using differential thermal (DTA), X-ray phase (XRD) microstructural (MSA) analysis, as well as by measuring the density and microhardness. It was found that the phase diagram of the PbSe-MnSe system is a quasi-binary section of the Pb-Mn-Se ternary system. A compound containing PbMnSe₂ in a 1:1 ratio of components is formed in the system. The PbMnSe₂ compound forms with an open maximum at 1150°C. The PbMnSe₂ compound crystallizes in the tetragonal system with lattice parameters: $a = 13.97$; $c = 8.20$ Å, $\rho_{\text{pycn.}} = 5.62$ g/cm³, $\rho_{\text{X-ray.}} = 5.66$ g/cm³.

Keywords: system, eutectic, liquidus, solid solution, microhardness.

Introduction

Obtaining new multicomponent semiconductor materials based on lead chalcogenides with desired characteristics requires obtaining reliable data on phase equilibria in the corresponding systems. Lead chalcogenides and alloys based on them have been studied in the literature of a large number of layered semiconductor compounds with binary and ternary thermoelectric properties [1-4]. Manganese and its ternary and more complex phases with various compounds are used as magnetic materials [5-8]. Ternary systems consisting of manganese chalcogenides have been studied in the literature [9-11].

From this point of view, the creation of new functional materials in the chemical interaction of PbSe and MnSe compounds is of scientific and practical importance.

The aim of this study is to study the chemical interactions of the PbSe-MnSe system, the construction of its phase diagram and the identification of the new phase and area of the solid solution.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to study the chemical interaction in the PbSe-MnSe system and construct its phase diagram.

Experimental part

PbSe and MnSe compounds were synthesized using the following purity elements: lead 99.98 %, selenium 99.998 % purity and electrolytic manganese. It should be noted that metallic manganese interacts with quartz glass. That is, quartz glass, unlike other elements, can react with manganese. Therefore, the inner

surface of the quartz ampoule is graphitized for the synthesis of compounds in the presence of manganese by the direct method.

We synthesized in special conditions. To synthesize the MnSe compound, very fine manganese is added to water, nitric acid is gradually added, and it is completely purified. Crushed manganese and selenium are weighed in a stoichiometric composition, placed in a quartz ampoule and the neck is closed by melting in a gas lamp by sucking in air. For synthesis, the mixture is placed in an inclined quartz ampoule at 300°C and shaken every time, and the synthesis continues for 2-3 days. Then the temperature was maintained at 500°C during the day.

After synthesis, the MnSe compound is in the form of an inhomogeneous powder. To obtain this compound in its entirety, it was crushed again and 200 atm. compressed under pressure and turned into a tablet. The pelleted samples were placed in a large-diameter quartz ampoule, the neck was sealed in an arc lamp with air suction. Then the quartz ampoule with the sample was subjected to heat treatment at 800°C for 240 hours.

After checking the obtained sample by X-ray phase analysis, the alloys of the PbSe-MnSe system were synthesized from the PbSe and MnSe components by the ampoule method in the temperature range of 1100-1200°C. Samples of the system were subjected to heat treatment for 240 hours at 600°C to bring them into equilibrium.

Equilibrium samples were studied by methods of physicochemical analysis.

The DTA of the alloys of the system was carried out on an NTR-73 device with a heating rate of 10 deg/min. Calibrated chromel - alumel thermocouples

were used, Al_2O_3 served as a reference. XRF was performed on an X-ray device model D-2 PHSER using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ -radiation Ni-filter. The MSA of the alloys of the system was studied using a MIM-8 metallographic microscope. When studying the microstructure of the alloys, an etchant with the composition conc. HNO_3 : $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 = 1:2$ etching time 20 s.

The microhardness of the alloys of the system was measured using a PMT-3 microhardness tester. When measuring microhardness, the error was 2.2-4.3 %. The density of the alloys of the system was determined by the pycnometric method, toluene served as the working liquid.

Results and its discussion

All alloys of the PbSe-MnSe system are resistant to environmental influences. With prolonged exposure to the open air, they gradually change. They dissolve only in strong mineral acids (HNO_3 , H_2SO_4) and strong alkalis (NaOH , KOH).

As a result of the thermal analysis of the alloys, it was found that two endothermic effects are observed on

the thermograms of the alloys. This indicates two-phase alloys of the PbSe-MnSe system. As a result of the thermal analysis of the alloys, it was found that two endothermic effects are observed on the thermograms of the alloys. This indicates two-phase alloys of the PbSe-MnSe system.

The phase diagram of the PbSe-MnSe system was built according to the results of physicochemical methods of analysis (Fig. 1).

The liquidus of the PbSe-MnSe system is surrounded by equilibrium monovariant curves of the δ -solid solution based on the PbSe compound, the PbMnSe_2 compound and the γ -solid solution. The system belongs to the quasi-binary eutectic type and is characterized by the formation of stable compound of MnPbSe_2 composition.

According to the results of microstructure analysis, it was established that in the PbSe-based system a solid solution with a concentration of 5 mol % MnSe is formed, while the solid solution region extends up to 2.5 mol % MnSe based on MnSe.

Fig. 3. T-x phase diagram of the PbSe-MnSe system.

To determine the area of a solid solution based on the PbSe compound, alloys containing 2, 3, 5, and 7 mol. % MnSe subjected to heat treatment at temperatures of 400 and 600°C for 100 hours and direct cooling in ice water. Then microstructural analysis was carried out on the samples. It has been determined that at room temperature the solubility based on the PbSe compound reaches up to 5 mol % MnSe, and at the eutectic temperature the solubility is 12 mol. % MnSe.

Some physical and chemical properties of the PbSe-MnSe system are shown in Table 1. As can be seen from Table 1, four different values of the microhardness of the PbSe-MnSe system alloys were obtained. The microhardness value (600-690) MPa corresponds to the microhardness of the δ -solid solution based on the PbSe compound, and the microhardness value is 1370 MPa of the PbMnSe_2 compound. The microhardness of the α -solid solution based on MnSe varies within (1900-1950) MPa.

Table 1.
Compositions, DTA results, microhardness measurements and density determination of alloys of the PbSe-MnSe system.

Composition mol %		Thermal effects, °C	Density, 10 ³ kg/m ³	Microhardness, MPa		
PbSe	MnSe			δ	PbMnSe ₂	α
				P=0,15 N		P=0,20 N
100	0,0	1080	8,26	600	-	-
95	5,0	945,1050	8,12	670	-	-
90	10	870,1020	7,91	690	-	-
85	15	850,975	7,75	690	-	-
80	20	850,920	7,56	690	-	-
75	25	850	7,31	Eutec.	Eutec.	-
70	30	850,940	7,21	-	1370	-
60	40	850,1100	6,87	-	1370	-
55	45	850,1120	6,86	-	1370	-
50	50	1150	6,68	-	1370	-
45	55	960,1125	6,34	-	1370	-
40	60	570,960	6,17	-	Eutec.	Eutec.
30	70	570,960,1160	5,83	-	-	1950
20	80	570,960	5,51	-	-	1950
10	90	580,960	4,90	-	-	1940

Conclusion

Thus, the PbSe-MnSe system was studied by the methods of physicochemical analysis and its T-x phase diagram was constructed. It has been established that the phase diagram of the PbSe-MnSe system is a quasi-binary section of the Pb-Mn-Se ternary system. A congruent PbMnSe₂ compound is formed in the system at 1150°C in a 1:1 component ratio.

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